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Overcoming matrix effects using the dilution approach in multiresidue methods for fruits and vegetables

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ABSTRACT

During recent years matrix effects in liquid chromatography coupled to tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) have quickly become a major concern in food analysis. The phenomenon of ion suppression can lead to errors in the quantification of the analytes of interest, as well as can affect detection capability, precision, and accuracy of the method. Sample dilution is an easy and effective method to reduce interfering compounds, and so, to diminish matrix effects. In this work, matrix effects of 53 pesticides in three different matrices (orange, tomato and leek) were evaluated. Several dilutions of the matrix were tested in order to study the evolution of signal suppression. Dilution of the extracts led to a reduction of the signal suppression in most of the cases. A dilution factor of 15 demonstrated to be enough to eliminate most of the matrix effects, opening the possibility to perform quantification with solvent based standards in the majority of the cases. In those cases where signal suppression could not be reduced, a possible solution would be to use stable isotope-labelled internal standards for quantification of the problematic pesticides.

Keywords: Liquid chromatography coupled to tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS); Pesticides; Matrix effect; Food analysis; Fruits and Vegetables; Dilutions

1. Introduction

Liquid chromatography coupled to tandem mass spectrometry with electrospray ionization (LC-ESI-MS/MS) is the most powerful qualitative and quantitative analytical technique that has increasingly been chosen as the preferred tool for pesticide residue analysis due to its undeniable capabilities [1,2]. Precision, robustness and high sensitivity and selectivity make it the perfect choice for multiresidue food analysis. Despite all these advantages, one important drawback of electrospray ionization that is being taken into consideration more and more in the past years is matrix effect. Matrix effects are a major concern in food analysis; they can be a serious problem as they can severely compromise quantitative analysis of the compounds at trace levels as well as method reproducibility [3,4]. Both electrospray ionization (ESI) and atmospheric pressure chemical ionization (APCI) suffer from this phenomenon [5], although evidence indicates that the electrospray interface is more likely to be impacted [6]. The mechanisms involved in this effect are diverse, and only some of them have been identified. One of the factors implied could be the presence of non volatile compounds coming either from the additives of the mobile phase or from the components of the sample, that would hinder the ionized analytes go out from the microdrops towards the gas phase [7,8]. Other studies [9,10] highlight the relevance of surface activity in the electrospray ionization process, as surface active matrix components can suppress the analyte ionization. Signal suppression has been found to be not only ionization mode dependent (ESI or APCI) but also dependent on the source design of the mass spectrometer [11,12] and on the mass spectrometry conditions [13]. In any case, signal suppression is an important issue that should be taken into account regarding food analysis.

Various strategies have been proposed with the aim to minimize or eliminate the matrix interferences, such as improve chromatographic selectivity in order to avoid coelution of the pesticides with the interfering matrix components [14–18], use different mobile phase strengths or modifiers [8,19], or revise sample preparation, with the intention to remove interferences [17,18,20–22]. Other authors try to compensate for matrix effects when matrix suppression phenomena cannot be eliminated, using different calibration techniques, such as quantification with matrix-matched calibration curves [23], standard addition [24], using stable isotope-labelled internal standards [22,25] or employing the ECHO peak technique, which simulates the use of internal standard, without the demand for an

isotope-labelled analog of the target analyte [26]. A recent approach for matrix effect compensation in multiresidue analysis is post column infusion, in which one single monitor substance is permanently added postcolumn [27]. Dilution is also an easy and effective method to get rid of interfering compounds, obtaining this way the injection of less matrix load into the chromatographic system, although in this case sensitivity is a key factor, given that it implies a reduction in the amount of analytes [28–30]. Nowadays, the appearance of new generation analytical systems in the market make possible this attempt, as highly sensitive instruments are available for these purposes. For that reason, sample dilution can be a very common approach for the next coming years in pesticide residue analysis. Usually, multiresidue methods inject 1 g of sample per mL, and such is the matrix load. Another advantage of the dilution approach is that it allows the introduction of less matrix components into the system, and thus, prolongs the useful life of the equipments. The applied LC-MS/MS multiresidue method was developed and validated in a previous work [31] for the analysis of pesticides in fruit juices. In that paper, 10-fold dilution of the extracts was applied, and the different matrix effects observed were studied. Nevertheless, further dilution factors were not investigated, neither the possible matrix components interfering with the pesticides. The aim of this work was to evaluate the effectiveness of different dilutions in pesticide analysis in three different vegetable matrices: orange, tomato and leek.

2. Experimental

2.1. Chemicals and reagents

2.1.1. Standards

Pesticide analytical standards of high purity (>98%) were purchased from Dr. Ehrenstorfer (Augsburg, Germany) and from Sigma–Aldrich (Steinheim, Germany). Individual pesticide stock solutions of all compounds (1000 mg L⁻¹) were prepared in acetonitrile or methanol and stored at –20 °C in the dark.

2.1.2. Solvents

HPLC-grade acetonitrile was supplied by J.T. Baker (Deventer, The Netherlands). A

Milli-Q-Plus ultra-pure water system from Millipore (Milford, MA, USA) was used throughout the study to obtain the HPLC-grade water used during the analyses.

2.1.3. Reagents

Formic acid and ammonium formate were purchased from Fluka (Buchs, Switzerland). Anhydrous magnesium sulphate was from Sigma-Aldrich (Madrid, Spain). PSA (primary-secondary amine) Bond Elut was obtained from Varian, Inc. (Palo Alto, CA, USA). Sodium chloride was acquired from Panreac (Barcelona, Spain). Trisodium citrate dihydrate was from Riedel-de Haën (Seetze, Germany), and disodium hydrogencitrate sesquihydrate was purchased from Fluka (Buchs, Switzerland).

2.2. Sample preparation

Orange, tomato and leek were purchased in the local market and were homogeneously chopped and stored at 4 °C before spiking and sample extraction. A previous analysis of the samples was performed in order to ensure that they did not contain any of the studied compounds, and these samples were selected as the blanks for all the experiments as well as for the preparation of matrix-matched standard solutions.

2.3. Real samples

In order to check the possible differences when quantifying with solvent based or with diluted matrix-matched standards in different commodities, 110 samples of diverse types of fruits and vegetables (apple, aubergine, broccoli, cauliflower, cucumber, garlic, green beans, leek, lemon, lettuce, lime, mandarin, onion, orange, pear, pepper, spring onion, tomato and zucchini) were purchased in supermarkets from the South of Spain, in Almería. All samples were stored at 4 °C before processing and at -18 °C until extraction and analysis.

2.4. Extraction procedure

The employed procedure was the European Committee for Standardization (CEN) Standard Method EN 15662 [32], which is a modification of the original QuEChERS

method [33] in which citrate salts are employed to buffer the extract and so adjust the pH to a compromise value of 5–5.5, where most acidic and basic labile pesticides are sufficiently stabilized [34]. The final extract obtained contained 1 g of sample per mL.

2.5. Preparation of the diluted extracts

With the purpose of studying the matrix effect behavior when the matrix load got reduced, different dilutions of the blank extracts were prepared, with dilution factors of 2, 5, 8, 10, 15, 25, 50 and 100, calculated as:

$$\text{Dilution factor} = \frac{V_f}{V_i}$$

where V_f is the final volume after dilution and V_i is the volume of the initial sample extract taken for dilution. For this reason, different aliquots of blank extract were diluted with acetonitrile, evaporated until near dryness under a gentle stream of nitrogen, and were reconstituted with the necessary volume of a mixture of acetonitrile: high purity water 1:9 (v/v) in order to obtain the desired dilution factor. In the case of the matrix-matched calibration standards, the evaporated matrix extracts were reconstituted with the solvent based calibration standards. Prior to LC–MS/MS analysis, the extracts were filtered through a 0.45 μm PTFE filter (Millex FG, Millipore, Milford, MA, USA).

2.6. LC–MS/MS analysis

Liquid chromatography–electrospray ionization–tandem mass spectrometry, in positive ion mode, was used to separate, identify, and quantify the target compounds. For the LC analysis, an Agilent 1200 HPLC system (Agilent Technologies, Wilmington, DE, USA) with a binary pump was used. The analytical column employed was a reversed-phase C8 of 150 mm \times 4.6 mm and 5 μm particle size (Agilent Zorbax Eclipse XDB). The mobile phases, A and B, were acetonitrile and high-purity water with 0.1% formic acid, respectively. The gradient program started with 10% of A, constant for 0.5 min, followed by a linear gradient up to 100% A in 15 min, and finishing with 100% A constant for 10 min. After this 25-min run time, 10 min of post-time followed using the initial 10% of A. The flow rate was

set constant at 0.6 mL/min during the whole process, and the injection volume was of 5 μ L. For the mass spectrometric analysis, a 5500 QTRAP MS/MS system (AB Sciex Instruments, Foster City, CA) was used, equipped with an turboionspray source operating in positive ionization mode, set with the following parameters: ion spray voltage (IS): 5500 V; curtain gas: 30 psi; nebulizer gas (GS1): 50 psi; auxiliary gas (GS2): 50 psi; source temperature: 550 °C. Nitrogen was used as the nebulizer and collision gas. Optimization of the compounds was performed in a previous work [31] by flow injection analysis (FIA), injecting individual standard solutions directly into the source. The best sensitivity in multiple reaction monitoring operation mode was achieved through the acquisition of selected reaction monitoring (SRM) transitions with “scheduled MRM mode”, with a time window of 90 s (the total number of SRM transitions was 106). For identification of the studied compounds two SRM transitions and a correct ratio between the abundances of the two optimized SRM transitions (SRM2/SRM1) were used, along with retention time matching. For quantification, the most intense SRM transition was selected. AB SCIEX Analyst software 1.5 was used for data acquisition and processing.

2.7. LC-Q-TOF-MS analysis

Liquid chromatography–quadrupole-time of flight-mass spectrometry (LC/ESI-Q-TOF-MS), in positive ion mode was used in order to evaluate the possible interfering matrix components coeluting with the compounds of interest, and so, to study the different matrix effects observed in the samples. Chromatographic separation was achieved using an HPLC system (consisting of a vacuum degasser, an autosampler, and a binary pump; Agilent Series 1200, Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA) equipped with a reversed phase C8 column of 150 mm \times 4.6 mm and 5 μ m particle size (Agilent Zorbax Eclipse XDB). The sample injection volume was 5 μ L. Mobile phases A and B were acetonitrile and water with 0.1% formic acid, respectively. The flow rate used was 0.6 mL/min. The gradient program started with 10% of A, constant for 0.5 min, followed by a linear gradient up to 100% A in 15 min, and finishing with 100% A constant for 10 min. After this 25-min run time, 7 min of post-time followed using the initial 10% of A. This HPLC system was connected to a quadrupole-time-of-flight mass spectrometer (Agilent 6530 Series Accurate Mass Q-TOF MS, Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA). The instrument operated in the 4 GHz High Resolution Mode. Ions were generated using an

electrospray ion source with Agilent Jet Stream Technology, operating in positive mode. The specific parameters for the Jet Stream source were the superheated nitrogen sheath gas temperature (400 ° C) and flow rate (12 L/min). Electrospray conditions were the following ones: capillary, 4000 V; nebulizer, 40 psi; drying gas, 10 L/min; gas temperature, 300 ° C; skimmer voltage, 65 V; octapole RF Vpp, 750 V; fragmentor voltage (in source CID fragmentation), 90 V. The mass axis was calibrated using the mixture provided by the manufacturer over the m/z 70–3200 range. A sprayer with a reference solution was used as continuous calibration using the following reference masses: 121.0509 and 922.0098 m/z (resolution: $19,500 \pm 500$ at 922.0098 m/z). For this work, the Q-TOF-MS instrument was used as a TOF-MS system working in the MS mode under full scan conditions. LC-TOF-MS accurate mass spectra were recorded across the range 80–1200 m/z . These data were processed with Agilent MassHunter Workstation Software (version B.02.00). The extracted ion chromatograms (XIC) of the protonated molecules of the compounds were obtained from the total ion chromatograms (TIC) with a 0.04 Da window. The accurate mass spectra of the analytes were achieved once the background of the XIC was subtracted.

2.8. Matrix effect studies

Matrix effects were evaluated along a range of concentrations, by injecting matrix-matched calibration curves with different dilution factors, but with the same concentrations for the points of the calibration curves, so only the matrix load was changing. Specifically, 10 different calibration curves were prepared, one in solvent, one in matrix with no dilution, and eight with different dilution factors: 2, 5, 8, 10, 15, 25, 50 and 100. Each calibration curve comprised seven concentration points, within the range from 0.1 to 500 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$. The matrix effect was studied by comparison of the slopes of the calibration curves in solvent and in matrix.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Matrix effects before dilutions

Matrix effects were studied by comparison of the slopes of the calibration curves in solvent and in matrix. Signal enhancement would occur if the percentage of the

difference between these slopes were positive. If it was negative, it would be indicative of signal suppression. Depending on the value of this percentage, we classified matrix effects into different categories. A percentage between -20% and 20% was considered as no matrix effect, because this variation would be close to the repeatability values. A medium matrix effect occurred when the values were between -50% and -20% or 20% and 50%, and a strong matrix effect would be below -50% or above +50%. In the three matrices studied, signal suppression was the effect observed. Of the three commodities evaluated, tomato was the one with less matrix effect, as 68% of the pesticides did not present relevant values. Almost a third part (30%) of the pesticides showed medium signal suppression, and only 2% of the compounds had a strong matrix effect. On the other side was leek, with the highest signal suppression: only 9% did not present signal suppression, 54% had a medium matrix effect and 37% of the pesticides showed a strong suppression. Orange exhibited no matrix effect for 43% of the pesticides, medium signal suppression for 29% and strong signal suppression for 28% of the compounds. Considering the results, it seemed necessary to apply dilution to the extracts in order to avoid matrix effects as much as possible.

3.2. Matrix effects after dilutions

Eight different dilution factors (2, 5, 8, 10, 15, 25, 50 and 100) for each matrix were studied in order to check the evolution of signal suppression with the reduction of the matrix load. In the case of tomato, most of the pesticides did not present signal suppression (68%) without dilution, and the majority of the remaining compounds that showed matrix effect (26%) improved before or with a dilution factor of 15. Only 6% of the pesticides needed a dilution factor of 50 or 100, and all of them improved with either one or another dilution. For orange the situation was different; 35% of the pesticides were free of matrix effect before dilution, 48% needed dilution up to a dilution factor of 15, and 17% of the compounds did not improve, even with the dilution factor of 100. In leek most of the pesticides (76%) required a dilution factor up to 15, and only 7% did not present signal suppression before dilution. A small percentage of compounds (4%) needed high dilutions and 13% still presented matrix effect even with the highest dilution factors studied. Fig. 1 summarizes the aforementioned. As we can see, each commodity presented a completely different behavior. An illustrative example is the case of ethiofencarb (Fig. 2a). In tomato, even without dilution the matrix effect is negligible, but the

same pesticide in leek or in orange presents a high signal suppression that gets reduced with dilution, but only to a small extent, not enough to reach the desired level. On the other hand, for acetamiprid signal suppression gets completely reduced after a dilution factor of 10 in all the studied matrices, as can be observed in Fig. 2b.

3.3. Analysis of the matrix interferences by LC-Q-TOF-MS

The fact that some pesticides still presented matrix effect after high dilution of the extracts suggested that there may be components of the matrix that, even at very low concentrations, would interact with the pesticides, producing the signal suppression. Fig. 3 represents this possible situation happening in the electrospray source, at different dilution levels. With a dilution factor of 100, even if the matrix load has decreased, there are still interfering components that bind to the pesticides, diminishing their signal. For this reason, in order to evaluate the possible interfering matrix components coeluting with the compounds of interest, and so, to study the different matrix effects observed in the samples, these were analysed by liquid chromatography–quadrupole-time of flight-mass spectrometry (LC/ESI-Q-TOF-MS) in positive ion mode. Orange, tomato and leek extracts were injected with and without dilution, and the full scan chromatograms were studied. An illustrative example is the one of ethiofencarb, previously mentioned in the former section. In orange, this pesticide shows high signal suppression, and even with a dilution factor of 100, the matrix effect remains (see Fig. 2). Examining the full scan chromatogram of a standard solution of ethiofencarb in orange extract we observed that there was a peak coeluting with the one corresponding to the studied pesticide. Furthermore, when we obtained the mass spectrum of ethiofencarb in a diluted orange extract, the mass of the protonated molecule appeared very small, and the base peak was at m/z 403.15610. Fig. 4(a) shows the extracted ion chromatograms of ethiofencarb (m/z 226.08963) and of the matrix component coeluting with it (m/z 403.15610). The mass spectrum of ethiofencarb appears in Fig. 4(b). Making use of the software tool “calculator” it was possible to elucidate the elemental composition of the unknown compound. This tool uses accurate mass measurements and the isotopic pattern to determine the most probable elemental composition. Fig. 4(c) shows the elemental composition confirmation of the matrix component. The best fit (with mass accuracy of -1.39 ppm) was $C_{21}H_{22}O_8$. Looking up in a chemical compound

database we found out that the formula corresponded to nobiletin, a flavonoid present in citrus peels. In fact, it is one of the major components of polymethoxyflavonoids in citrus fruits, and possesses anticancer, antiviral and anti-inflammatory activity [35]. Its presence in citrus peel has been stated before by LC-MS analysis [36,37]. The identification of the interfering compound was possible due to one of the main attributes of TOF instruments, which is their accurate mass measurements, giving the elemental composition of parent and fragment ions [38]. The reliability of the method depends heavily on the ruggedness of the TOF instrument in order to provide consistently accurate mass measurements within a fixed mass error tolerance. Typically, the measurement of accurate masses within 5 ppm is widely accepted for the verification of the elemental composition [39]. The Q-TOF system used for this work has demonstrated mass accuracy values of <2 ppm in most cases, regardless of the matrices or the concentration level.

3.4. Survey of the studied pesticides in real samples

After studying the possibility of reducing matrix effects with dilution of the samples, the next objective was to verify if quantification of real samples could be achievable using solvent based calibration curves. With the aim of checking the possible differences when quantifying with solvent based or with diluted matrix-matched standards in different commodities, 110 samples of diverse types of fruits and vegetables were purchased in super- markets from the South of Spain, in Almería. Apple, aubergine, broccoli, cauliflower, cucumber, garlic, green beans, leek, lemon, lettuce, lime, mandarin, onion, orange, pear, pepper, spring onion, tomato and zucchini were the selected samples. These were extracted with the QuEChERS method, were diluted 15 times before analyses and were quantified with matrix matched calibration curves with the matrix load diluted 15 times. This dilution factor was chosen because with it, most of the pesticides did not present signal suppression in the three studied commodities. From the 110 samples, 41 of them (37%) were blank in our scope, or contained pesticides at levels lower than $1 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$. From the positive findings, a total number of 21 pesticides were found, among which one – omethoate – is not included in Directive 91/414/EEC, and therefore it should not be used in the EU. Tebuconazole, thiacloprid and imazalil were the pesticides mostly found in the samples.

With the purpose of verifying how the matrix components could affect

quantification, all the samples were re-analysed quantifying with solvent based calibration curves. The differences between both concentrations obtained were expressed as a percentage. Table 1 summarizes the results. The total number of occurrences was 124, that is, in all the samples there were 124 positive findings of pesticides. Of these, 65% presented variations in quantification within the range from 0 to 20%, which we considered that were negligible, allowing the possibility of performing quantification with solvent based calibration curves, and so avoiding the use of matrix-matched calibration curves. On the other hand, 18% of the cases showed differences from 20 to 40%, which are significant, so these events should be studied individually. Finally, 17% of the occurrences presented values higher than 40%, which corresponded to 6 pesticides (Carbendazim, cyproconazole, imazalil, indoxacarb, pyriproxyfen and tebuconazole) of the 21 found. In these cases, quantification with solvent based calibration curves should be avoided, as the errors could be significant. From the results obtained we can say that it is not possible to generalize, and specific problems should be approached individually in order to achieve the best results.

4. Conclusions

For this work, different dilutions of the matrix were tested in order to study the signal suppression of 53 pesticides in three different matrices: orange, tomato and leek. Dilution of the extracts led to a reduction of the signal suppression in most of the cases. A dilution factor of 15 demonstrated to be enough to eliminate most of the matrix effects, opening the possibility to perform quantification with solvent based standards in the majority of the cases. In those cases where signal suppression could not be reduced, a possible solution would be to use stable isotope-labelled internal standards for quantification of the problematic pesticides. On the basis of the results, it can be concluded that sample dilution proved to be very advantageous, as it was easy to implement and very effective regarding diminishing of signal suppression.

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Fig. 1. Distribution of the pesticides in the three matrices studied according to how matrix effect gets affected with dilution of the matrix.

Fig. 2. Illustration of signal suppression of ethiofencarb (a) and acetamidrid (b) in leek (green), orange (orange) and tomato (red) when applying different dilutions. (For interpretation of the references to color in text, the reader is referred to the web version of the article.)

Fig. 3. Simulation of the droplets behavior in the electro spray source at different dilution levels.

Fig. 4. Identification of the matrix component of the orange (nobiletin) interfering with ethiofencarb analysis. (a) Extracted ion chromatograms of both ethiofencarb and the interfering component. (b) Accurate mass spectrum of the peak corresponding to ethiofencarb. (c) Elemental composition confirmation of nobiletin by accurate mass measurements, isotopic pattern and double bond equivalents.

Table 1. Differences between quantification of the real samples with 15-times diluted-matrix matched calibration curves or with solvent based calibration curves.

Difference (%)	Number of cases	Percentage of cases	Numer of pesticides
<20	81	65	20
20-40	22	18	9
>40	21	17	6
Total	124	100	21

Supplementary data

Table 1 Values of the instrumental settings optimized for each compound in LC-ESI-MS/MS: precursor ion, declustering potential (DP), entrance potential (EP), product ions and their collision energies (CE).

	Retention time (min)	Precursor Ion (m/z)	DP (V)	EP (V)	Product Ion 1 (m/z)	CE 1 (eV)	Product Ion 2 (m/z)	CE 2 (eV)
Acephate	4.6	184.0	47.00	14.00	143.0	16.00	125.0	27.00
Acetamiprid	9.6	223.0	100.00	7.00	126.0	30.00	56.0	21.00
Albendazole	10.2	265.7	120.00	10.00	234.0	30.00	192.0	40.00
Azoxystrobin	14.0	404.2	100.00	5.00	372.0	21.00	343.9	33.00
Benalaxyl	15.7	326.2	110.00	8.00	208.1	21.00	294.2	16.00
Bupirimate	13.3	316.7	110.00	5.00	166.1	32.00	272.1	27.00
Cambendazole	8.3	303.0	144.00	7.00	261.1	26.00	217.0	40.00
Carbendazim	6.1	192.0	200.00	9.00	160.1	27.00	132.0	41.00
Carbofuran	12.1	222.0	91.00	5.00	165.1	18.00	123.1	31.00
Chloroxuron	13.8	291.0	110.00	7.00	72.1	54.00	164.1	24.00
Chromafenozide	14.8	395.2	62.00	9.00	175.1	29.00	132.9	34.00
Cyproconazole	13.6	292.1	170.00	9.00	70.1	58.00	125.0	44.00
Deet	12.5	192.0	160.00	11.00	119.1	26.00	91.0	41.00
Diazinon	16.3	304.6	100.00	8.00	169.0	30.00	153.1	27.00
Diethofencarb	13.9	268.0	76.00	4.00	226.1	14.00	180.1	23.00

Difenoconazole	15.4	405.9	100.00	5.00	250.9	36.00	337.0	24.00
Difenoconazole	12.4	287.0	150.00	12.00	72.0	23.00	123.3	25.00
Diuron	12.5	233.0	64.00	11.00	72.0	22.00	160.0	35.00
Ethiofencarb	12.7	226.1	60.00	5.00	107.0	28.00	164.1	11.00
Fenbendazole	11.6	300.1	150.00	8.00	268.0	27.00	159.0	47.00
Fenobucarb	14.0	208.1	94.00	4.00	94.9	25.00	152.1	12.00
Fenuron	12.4	165.1	40.00	10.00	72.0	26.00	120.0	24.00
Flazasulfuron	13.0	408.0	57.00	4.00	182.0	29.00	301.1	22.00
Fluacrypyrim	16.6	427.2	81.00	8.00	145.1	42.00	205.0	13.00
Fluometuron	12.3	233.1	73.00	13.00	72.0	34.00	160.1	39.00
Imazalil	9.9	297.8	125.00	5.00	158.9	34.00	255.9	24.00
Indoxacarb	16.3	528.0	120.00	13.00	249.2	24.00	292.9	18.00
Isoprocab	13.1	194.0	60.00	6.00	94.9	18.00	152.1	11.00
Isoproturon	12.4	207.1	70.00	5.00	72.0	27.00	165.1	19.00
Metalaxyl	12.4	280.1	94.00	12.00	220.0	17.00	248.0	14.00
Metamitron	8.8	202.7	80.00	5.00	103.9	30.00	175.1	25.00
Methamidophos	4.0	142.0	73.00	5.00	94.0	21.00	125.2	19.00
Methoxyfenozide	14.6	369.3	65.00	12.00	149.0	23.00	133.1	35.00
Metolachlor	15.2	284.0	100.00	11.00	252.1	18.00	176.1	36.00
Monocrotophos	7.3	224.0	60.00	11.00	192.7	11.00	127.0	20.00
Monuron	11.1	199.1	120.00	10.00	72.0	23.00	126.0	37.00

Myclobutanil	14.2	289.1	38.00	6.00	70.0	23.00	125.1	46.00
Omethoate	5.5	214.0	66.00	8.00	125.0	29.00	155.0	23.00
Oxamyl	7.3	242.0	90.00	3.00	72.0	36.00	121.1	18.00
Pirimicarb	7.8	238.7	50.00	7.00	72.1	38.00	182.2	23.00
Pirimiphos methyl	16.4	306.1	110.00	11.00	108.0	42.00	164.1	28.00
Promecarb	14.2	208.1	80.00	9.00	151.1	14.00	109.0	23.00
Propamocarb	5.7	189.1	29.00	6.00	101.9	25.00	144.1	16.00
Propaphos	15.1	304.8	90.00	8.00	221.0	19.00	263.0	10.00
Propazine	13.6	230.0	100.00	3.00	146.0	30.00	188.0	24.00
Pyridaphenthion	14.4	341.0	100.00	7.00	189.1	36.00	205.0	34.00
Pyrimidifen	14.0	377.7	130.00	5.00	184.0	35.00	150.0	51.00
Pyriproxyfen	17.1	322.1	100.00	9.00	227.0	21.00	96.0	20.00
Tebuconazole	14.4	308.1	80.00	8.00	70.1	60.00	125.1	57.00
Tetraconazole	14.4	372.0	110.00	4.00	159.0	43.00	70.0	65.00
Thiacloprid	10.5	253.0	110.00	7.00	125.9	34.00	186.0	19.00
Triadimenol	13.5	296.1	50.00	13.00	70.0	40.00	227.1	14.00
Triazophos	14.9	314.1	120.00	8.00	162.1	25.00	286.0	16.00

Table 2 Occurrence of pesticides in fruits and vegetables purchased from the local stores.

Food commodity	Pesticides	No. Samples	Range of concentrations ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$)
Apple (12 samples)	Acetamiprid	1	1.5
	Carbendazim	1	17.7
	Lenacil	1	6.8
	Metamitron	1	6.2
	Methoxyfenozide	2	1.9-5.0
	Myclobutanil	2	1.3-2.9
	Pirimicarb	1	15.5
	Tebuconazole	1	16.6
	Thiacloprid	5	1.0-10.4
	Blanks	3	-
Aubergine (2 samples)	Blanks	2	-
Brocoli (2 samples)	Metalaxyl	1	164.7
	Blanks	1	-
Cauliflower (2 samples)	Blanks	2	-
Cucumber (3 samples)	Metalaxyl	1	1.1
	Myclobutanil	1	22.6
	Propamocarb	1	2.4
	Blanks	1	-
Garlic (2 samples)	Blanks	2	-
Green beans (4 samples)	Azoxystrobin	1	2.6
	Blanks	3	-
Leek (2 samples)	Blanks	2	-
Lemon (4 samples)	Imazalil	4	2075.9-3958.7
	Blanks	0	-
Lettuce (8 samples)	Acetamiprid	1	43.0
	Azoxystrobin	3	3.9-140.1
	Indoxacarb	2	5.3-8.4
	Lenacil	1	15.1
	Metalaxyl	2	2.1-28.1
	Propamocarb	1	1.2
	Blanks	2	-
Lime (1 samples)	Carbendazim	1	4.0
	Imazalil	1	231.2
	Blanks	0	-
Mandarin (1 samples)	Imazalil	1	734.7
	Blanks	0	-
Onion (4 samples)	Blanks	4	-
Orange	Carbendazim	2	5.8-14.9

(6 samples)	Imazalil	6	506.6-1644.6
	Omethoate	1	2.5
	Tebuconazole	1	1.4
	Blanks	0	-
Pear (13 samples)	Carbendazim	2	6.0-15.1
	Difenoconazole	4	3.0-7.4
	Tebuconazole	5	2.0-9.0
	Tetraconazole	3	2.6-2.7
	Thiacloprid	4	1-55.4
	Blanks	4	-
Pepper (11 samples)	Metalaxyl	1	1
	Methoxyfenozide	1	29.9
	Pirimicarb	1	1.5
	Pirimiphos methyl	1	6.4
	Pyriproxifen	1	20.6
	Blanks	7	-
Spring onion (1 samples)	Blanks	1	-
Tomato (29 samples)	Acetamiprid	8	1.6-85.7
	Azoxystrobin	3	1.7-32.7
	Carbendazim	2	1.2-23.2
	Cyproconazole	2	3.3-3.4
	Diethofencarb	2	1.2-1.7
	Difenoconazole	1	5.3
	Indoxacarb	5	1.5-10.9
	Methoxyfenozide	2	2.5-45.7
	Myclobutanil	6	1.2-20.6
	Propamocarb	3	1.3-4.8
	Pyriproxifen	4	5.0-62.6
	Tebuconazole	8	4.8-16.9
	Tetraconazole	1	5.2
	Thiacloprid	4	1.3-13.9
Blanks	5	-	
Zucchini (3 samples)	Azoxystrobin	1	1.8
	Omethoate	1	2.3
	Blanks	1	-